

Facilitating Privacy Attitudes & Behaviors with Affective Visual Design

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Abstract. We all too often must consent to information collection at an early stage of digital interactions, during application sign-up. Paying low attention to privacy policies, we are rarely aware of processing practices. Drawing on multidisciplinary research, we hypothesize that privacy policies presenting information in a way that triggers affective responses, combined with intrinsic characteristics of an individual, may influence privacy attitudes. Through an online quasi-experiment ($N = 88$), we investigate how affect, illustration type, individual characteristics and privacy concerns may influence willingness to disclose personal information and privacy awareness. Our results partially confirm these assumptions. We found that the affect may have an impact on privacy awareness. The willingness to disclose is not affected by visual design but by stable psychological constructs. We discuss the applicability of our findings in interface design and for future research.

Keywords: Privacy · Usability · Attitude · Behavior · Affect · Emotion.

1 Introduction

Due to a large and growing number of privacy and security violations, privacy has been recognized as a critical issue by the governments and policymakers. Despite awareness of privacy breaches, people may over-disclose their personal information in everyday online activities [1]. Increasing reliance on technology makes it crucial to protect individuals' privacy, but not all of the current solutions include appropriate privacy-protective measures. Hence, legal protections have been established, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) aiming to protect users' privacy and focusing on informed consent as the primary disclosure enabler [10].

The decisions shaping information disclosure usually begin at an early stage of interactions: during the sign-up process. At that point, the user must consent to the service providers' data collection and processing practices. As privacy management is not a primary task, the users may disregard data processing information presented in the privacy policy. Current methods of policy display may advance such negligence by inadequate user interface (UI) design, showing

information in a non-transparent and challenging to comprehend manner [27]. For instance, it is a common practice to collect the consent with a simplistic affirmative action: a tick of a checkbox approving “understanding” of the terms hidden under the hyperlinked text.

Searching for the ways to overcome these issues around consent, and to understand how to make consent more meaningful, we focus on affective states elicited by visual design and illustration type. In this paper, we assess their influence on information disclosure and privacy awareness in the context of the online sign-up process. Moreover, we look into the relationship between individual characteristics (personality traits), affect and privacy concerns. The objective of this research is to identify how to improve privacy awareness at an early stage of interaction and to advance knowledge about privacy attitudes and behaviors. Our findings show that affective framing and arousal alter privacy-related attitudes and behaviors. The results also indicate how people may feel hopeless during early-stage interactions, lacking control over their data.

2 Background

The GDPR aims to protect the privacy rights of users and has a direct impact on online service providers [10]. The regulation provides a set of strict rules regarding data collection and processing practices. According to the regulation, online services must provide users with understandable and transparent information about data provision practices. Further, the GDPR enforces precise requirements regarding informed consent.

We follow the GDPR guidelines and test different designs of the privacy policy that aim to provide users with transparent information. We draw on the definition of transparency and consent being informed by designing structured privacy policy, which emphasizes information collection and processing practices.

2.1 Visual Display, Learning and Attention

Past research has shown that visual stimuli may have an influence on attention and can improve learning [30]. Affective images may influence decisions: the more affective the images, the more weight is placed on impression formation and decision-making [34]. Further, pictures may have an impact on a performance level; when external representations are available, the effects of the previously faced visualization decrease, because individuals are less dependent on the existing mental images [30]. Visual design may influence attention and affect memory, when it includes animations, anthropomorphic designs, clear layouts such as division into columns and more [36, 38].

In the context of privacy, anthropomorphic designs may increase personal information disclosure [25, 3]. Past work demonstrated that text was insufficiently communicating privacy information, and a different approach should be applied to enhance usability [2]. Such method must be carefully crafted, ensuring that

it does not lead to over-symbolic and cluttered representations (e.g., unnecessary icons). Moreover, comic strips were found to increase users' attention [37]. Comics convey a message in a way that relates to emotions, enabling a greater understanding of the outlined issues [26]. Past research revealed that the end-user agreements presented in abbreviated style divided into short sections, elicited positive attitudes, increasing comprehension and time of exposure [39]. Hence, our first research question is as follows:

RQ1: Does different illustration type applied in privacy policies influence privacy awareness and willingness to disclose information?

2.2 Factors Related to Decision-Making

Many factors influence decisions. At times, choices might be rational, e.g., when based on costs and benefits calculus requiring the decision-maker to possess all the necessary information to compute the most optimal outcome. Peoples' decisions can also sway from objective rationality and described by simple heuristics that enable effortless decisions, which can be made with limited information and within a short time [35, 18].

Affect and Information Processing One of simple heuristics is the affect heuristic, when people make judgments based on subjective evaluations by adding either positive or negative value to the decision outcome [12]. The *affect-as-information* hypothesis postulates that affective states have cognitive consequences mediated by the subjective experience of affect [5]. Thus, emotions occur, and this feeling has a significant impact on cognitive processing, providing conscious information from unconscious appraisal situations. Such feelings can guide immediate actions. Affective reactions in object-focused individuals may create experiences, e.g., liking or disliking, resulting in a higher or lower evaluation of an object. Similarly, the *feelings-as-information* theory proposes that positive affect indicates that a given situation is safe [31]. Negative affect signifies that a situation is unsafe, and more cognitive processing is needed. Therefore, positive affect may serve as an incentive to rely on internal thoughts and inclinations, whereas negative affect should direct attention to new, external information. In sum, affect relates to recall, thought generation and processing of new, external information. Affective reactions may result from an external stimulus, such as the way information is presented or semantic context, in which the situation takes place.

In the context of privacy, affect may shape risk perceptions [19]. It may have a lasting impact on privacy beliefs, e.g., in an e-commerce environment [22]. Further, negative valence may increase privacy attitude and decrease sharing, while positive valence may increase sharing attitude and decrease privacy attitude [6]. Based on past research, we raise the following questions:

RQ2: Do the different designs of privacy policy elicit affective responses?

RQ3: Does affective framing applied in the design of privacy policies influence privacy awareness and willingness to disclose?

Antecedents of Privacy-Related Decision-Making In this article, we aim to focus on some of the factors identified in the APCO (Antecedents→ Privacy Concerns→Outcomes) framework [7]. Following this model, we investigate privacy awareness and willingness to disclose as outcomes, and personality characteristics and privacy concerns as outcomes’ antecedents. Personality traits may have an influence on privacy concerns [24]. The agreeableness, conscientiousness, and imagination can contribute to the formulation of “Concerns for Privacy” [17]. Additionally, personality traits may influence information disclosure [14]. Further, past research shows the effects of privacy concerns on disclosure, moderated by psychological biases and mental shortcuts [21, 28]. Information disclosure may result from personal concerns, perceived threats, or simply user experience [20]. Considering the APCO model and past research, we raise the following question:

RQ4: Do individual characteristics, and privacy concerns influence awareness and willingness to disclose information?

3 Methods

To address our research questions, we developed an online quasi-experiment (the random assignment was present, but the experiment lacked a control group) [32]. The dependent variables were a willingness to disclose information, privacy awareness and affective states (valence and arousal). The two independent variables were the design proprieties: affective framing (positive and negative) and illustration type (anthropomorphic and human). We controlled for the influence of other variables, such as privacy concerns and personality traits.

3.1 Participants

The participants were found online on Reddit (“Sample Size” subreddit). The respondents had to be at least 18 years old and fluent in English. Participation in the study was entirely voluntary; no financial compensation was offered. We collected 99 responses. After data screening, the sample size reduced to 88. Almost half of the respondents was females ($N = 40$, 45%), and the majority was between 18-34 years old ($N = 37$, 42%). Most of the participants completed some higher education ($N = 50$, 56.%). The sample included participants from various countries, mostly English speaking (UK, USA and Canada $N = 49$, 55.6%, 11 participants did not provide nationality).

3.2 Study Design

Before the study, the respondents had to acknowledge an informed consent form. Majority of questions were mandatory to answer, apart from the demographic questions. To reduce ordering effects, when possible, we implemented randomization (the questionnaires’ items were arranged in a different order across participants). The study consisted of five phases.

Fig. 1. Examples of images accompanying policy texts. From left: anthropomorphic positive, anthropomorphic negative, human positive, human negative.

Phase 1: Questionnaires We measured *The Big Five* personality traits with the instrument acquired from Donallann et al. [8]. This method was validated in past research, and it is a concise instrument that suits the relatively long study. The scale contains 20 items (four items measure each trait: extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism and imagination). Next, the participants were presented with questions measuring their affective states. We used the “Affective Self Report” acquired from Jenkins et al. [15]. The scale consists of ten items measuring the two-dimensional structure of affect: valence and arousal.

Phase 2: Vignette and Interactive Task We asked the participants to imagine that they were signing up for a well-being application, which aims to help to improve both physical and mental well-being. The participants were advised that the app offered social functionality, such as sharing and connecting with other users. They were instructed that over the next few pages, they would be exposed to the fictional sign-up form, asking for personal information, such as email address and password, but none of this data would be collected. Next, the participants were prompted to acknowledge the privacy policy. There were four different policy designs (Figure 1): (1) a positively framed text with anthropomorphic representation, (2) a positively framed text with human representation, (3) a negatively framed text with anthropomorphic representation, (4) a negatively framed text with human representation. We shortened the policy and structured the text into thematically arranged paragraphs, with a header describing a particular section, e.g., “How we use your data”. The Gunning’s Fogg text readability score was 12.7, meaning that the text should be understandable by high school seniors [40]. Each privacy policy finished with a binary choice: to “Agree” or to “Disagree”.

Phase 3: Interactive Task’s Exit Questionnaires We measured the willingness to disclose information. We created a Likert-type instrument, based on the information disclosure scale proposed by Joinson et al. [16]. The participants were asked to think back about the sign-up process and state which pieces of information they would have disclosed. The scale consisted of 14 items of personal information, e.g., number of sexual partners. The responses scored 1 (“I would disclose”) or 0 (“I would not disclose”). We took the 2nd measurement of the affect with the same instrument as in Phase 1, presenting participants with their scores and asking whether they wished to adjust them.

Phase 4: Questionnaires We measured privacy awareness as the knowledge of the privacy policy. We built a quiz-like questionnaire to assess how much of the privacy information the participants remembered. We used ten questions related to the highlighted text of the privacy policies. The scores were binary: “True” (correct) or “False” (incorrect). To measure privacy concerns, we used an instrument acquired from Malhotra et al. [23]. The Likert scale contains six items presenting privacy statements. Participants were asked to declare to what extent they agreed or disagreed with the statements (1 – strongly disagree to 7 – strongly agree). We asked the participants for basic demographic information: gender, age, nationality, and level of education.

Phase 5: Open-Ended Question We asked the participants to explain why during the interactive task they “Agreed”, or “Disagreed” with policy. The participants were required to provide an answer.

Ethical review The study received ethical approval from the Karlstad University Ethical Review Board. There were no harms or risks associated with the study. We ensured that the data collection and processing was compliant with the GDPR. When possible, we applied data anonymization measures. No sensitive personal data was collected.

Variables Applied in the Model The between-subject variables were affective framing (AFES: positive or negative), and illustration type (ILLT: anthropomorphic and human). The four dependent variables were: post-stimulus valence (VALP), post-stimulus arousal (AROP), willingness to disclose (WILD) and privacy awareness (PRAW). The covariates were: pre-stimulus arousal (PRAR) and valence (PREV); conscientiousness (CONS) and neuroticism (NEUR) (extraversion and agreeableness were removed, as they had no effect); privacy concerns (PRIC).

4 Results

The assessment of latent variables collected through self-reported instruments requires checks of validity and reliability. We used qualitative methods to check the face and content validity, and quantitative methods to check the criterion validity. To assess reliability, we applied the Cronbach α estimate, accepting scores higher than 0.7 [13].

Personality Traits We ran Principal Component Analysis (PCA). Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure was 0.70, and Bartlett’s test for sphericity was significant, $p < 0.001$ [29]. Personality types did not load as expected into five factors [8], but into six factors, with *imagination* loading incorrectly. We removed this trait from further analysis. For each of the remaining constructs, we ran reliability tests, which all scored well, $\alpha > 0.7$.

Affective Self Report (ASR) We measured two dimensions: valence and arousal. The scale consists of ten semantic differential items, five per each di-

mension. For both pre-, and post-stimulus measures, we ran PCA to check factorability. The KMO scores were good (pre: 0.84 and post: 0.86), and Bartlett's tests for sphericity significant ($p < 0.001$) [11]. The scores did not load properly. Hence we removed two items: "Tired-Energetic" and "Indifferent-Curious". We used five items to compute valence, and three to compute arousal.

Willingness to Disclose The recommended estimate of scale reliability for dichotomous data is KR20 [4]. However, since Cronbach's α is a generalization of KR20, we interpreted its scores. The Cronbach's α was good, 0.90 ($M = 6.68$, $\sigma^2 = 18.05$, $SD = 4.25$).

Privacy Awareness The privacy awareness scores were measured as dichotomous data (True = 1 or False = 0). However, as privacy awareness was not measuring a latent construct but assessed knowledge, we did not perform reliability checks. We applied an average of scores in further statistical analysis ($M = 0.58$, $SD = 0.13$).

Privacy Concerns The results of PCA were satisfying. However, Cronbach's α reliability for six items was below the commonly accepted threshold. Hence, we re-ran the analysis and used only four of the scale items to compute the variable.

4.1 Statistical Analysis

We performed multivariate analysis of covariance (MANCOVA). Before the test, we checked assumptions (outliers with Mahalanobis distance; linearity; multicollinearity; univariate and multivariate normality; homogeneity and homoscedasticity). Next, we ran the final model and reevaluated homogeneity with a Box's test of equality of covariance matrices ($p = 0.15$) and Levene's tests of equality of variances ($p > 0.05$). The results of MANCOVA, using the Wilk's Lambda as a criterion, are presented in Table 1.

In the model, the significant adjustors of the combined dependent variables were PRAR ($\eta_p^2 = 0.80$), PREV ($\eta_p^2 = 0.78$) and PRIC ($\eta_p^2 = 0.21$). After estimating out the covariates, AFES had a significant effect on combined dependent variables, $\eta_p^2 = 0.12$ but ILLT had not. Similarly, there was no significant interaction effect between AFES and ILLT on combined dependent variables.

We used individual ANCOVAs to examine the data further. PRAR was a significant adjustor of AROP ($\eta_p^2 = 0.50$), VALP ($\eta_p^2 = 0.05$), and WILD ($\eta_p^2 = 0.05$). The scores of arousal pre-, and post-stimuli were highly correlated, $r = 0.84$, $p < 0.01$. There was a negative correlation with VALP, suggesting that with an increase of arousal, there is a decrease of valence, $r = -0.331$, $p < 0.01$.

PREV had a significant influence on VALP ($\eta_p^2 = 0.52$). There was a significant positive correlation between PREV and VALP, $r = 0.77$, $p < 0.01$.

PRIC significantly influenced AROP ($\eta_p^2 = 0.08$), VALP ($\eta_p^2 = 0.11$) and WILD ($\eta_p^2 = 0.13$). We found significant positive correlations between privacy concerns and arousal, $r = 0.27$, $p < 0.01$ (implying an increase in arousal among participants with greater concerns). There was a significant negative correlation between PRIC and WILD, $r = -0.38$, $p < 0.01$ (indicating that people with greater concerns have a lower willingness to disclose).

Table 1. MANCOVA: effects of affective framing and illustration types on the dependent variables: post-stimuli arousal (AROP), post-stimuli valence (VALP), willingness to disclose (WILD) and privacy awareness (PRAW).

	Multivariate		Univariate			
	Wilks's λ	$F(4, 76)$	AROP	VALP	WILD	PRAW
Covariates						
PRAR	0.19	77.21**	79.96**	4.03*	4.70*	1.61
PREV	0.21	70.64**	1.31	85.32**	0.19	3.41
CONS	0.91	1.72	0.54	0.62	2.32	4.2*
NEUR	0.90	2.03	2.24	1.66	5.45*	0.76
PRIC	0.78	5.13*	7.31*	10.02*	11.59*	2.08
Fixed factors						
AFES	0.87	2.66*	4.74*	3.21	0.90	6.33*
ILLT	0.97	0.54	0.22	0.02	0.06	1.28
AFES*ILLT	0.91	1.74	4.97*	1.01	0.24	<0.01

Note: Significance values are based on * $p < 0.05$ and ** $p < 0.001$.

There were no significant effects of NEUR on WILD and CONS to PRAW. Therefore, our results suggest that the *Big Five* personality traits are weak influencers of privacy related attitudes and behaviors.

We found a significant effect of AFES on AROP ($\eta_p^2 = 0.06$). There was a difference in means of the two levels of AFES on arousal ($p < 0.05$). The scores for post-stimuli arousal were higher among the participants assigned to negative ($M = 4.01$, $SD = 0.11$), than to positive ($M = 3.67$, $SD = 0.10$) stimulus exposure. The effect of AFES on VALP was not significant. However, the valence scores were higher after exposure to positive ($M = 4.30$, $SD = 0.11$) than to negative ($M = 4.00$, $SD = 0.12$) stimulus.

AFES had a significant influence on PRAW, $\eta_p^2 = 0.07$. The participants exposed to the negative stimulus scored higher ($M = 0.62$, $SD = 0.01$), than those exposed to the positive stimulus ($M = 0.55$, $SD = 0.01$). We did not find any effect of the illustration type on the dependent variables.

There was a significant interaction effect between AFES and ILLT on post-stimulus arousal ($\eta_p^2 = 0.60$) (Figure 2). The arousal's mean was higher for the anthropomorphic negative affective state ($M = 4.16$, $SD = 0.16$), than for human negative affective state ($M = 3.87$, $SD = 0.16$). This effect was reversed, and arousal means for the positive anthropomorphic design were lower ($M = 3.45$, $SD = 0.16$) than for the positive human design ($M = 3.89$, $SD = 0.15$).

4.2 Exploratory Findings

In the open-ended question, we asked participants why they “Agreed” (AGR) or “Disagreed” (DIS) with the privacy policy. Only 23 participants selected to

Fig. 2. Estimated marginal means for post-stimulus arousal (AROP). Covariates appearing in the model are evaluated at the following values: PRAR=3.58, PREV=4.50, PRIC=4.57, CONS=12.52, NEUR=11.32.

disagree, and we did not find any significant associations between agreement with policies and the policy design.

All cases where participants stated that they had selected an option only to pursue the study were removed from the analysis, resulting in $N = 77$ answers (DIS $N = 22$, AGR $N = 55$). Two researchers read through the answers and, in a systematic manner, identified justification of the participants' choices (Table 2).

Disagreeing Sixteen reasons surfaced during the analysis of answers from the respondents who disagreed. The most frequent reason related to the *lack of control*, while sharing personal data with *social media* platforms was the second most frequent. E.g., “The lack of control over personal data shared with third parties as well as the catch-22 of only using the Social platforms/forums if data was shared”. Participants stated that the policy was *unacceptable*, or they did not *trust* the provider, e.g., because the data would be stored abroad: “The US govt could access this data, and it is not trustworthy”.

Some respondents stated that there was not enough information about why data was collected (*necessity, fairness, personal information collection*). A few answers were *emotionally* loaded, e.g., “The main reason is that the pictures spelled it out in clear form what would happen to my information. As a result it made me sceptical to share my information”. Only a few responses hinted that *pictures help* or mentioned *usability*, e.g., “Also, the drawings definitely gave the impression the policy was unfair”.

Table 2. The main reasons for selecting “Disagree” and “Agree” with privacy policy [*Reason*(frequency of appearance)].

Disagree	<i>Lack of control</i> (13), <i>Social media</i> (7), <i>Unacceptable</i> (7), <i>Trust</i> (6), <i>Necessity of collection</i> (5), <i>Personal information</i> (4), <i>Fairness</i> (4), <i>Emotional response</i> (4), <i>Protection</i> (3), <i>Usability</i> (3), <i>Health information</i> (3), <i>Pictures help</i> (2), <i>Unauthorized sharing</i> (2), <i>Tracking</i> (1), <i>Legal requirement</i> (1), <i>Manipulation</i> (1)
Agree	<i>Lack of choice</i> (28), <i>Want to use app</i> (18), <i>Habit</i> (14), <i>Trust</i> (10), <i>Don't care</i> (8), <i>Not worse than others</i> (6), <i>Control</i> (5), <i>Somewhat clear</i> (4), <i>I can handle privacy</i> (4), <i>Protection</i> (3), <i>Legal requirement</i> (2), <i>Sunk cost</i> (2), <i>Consent if changes</i> (2), <i>Social media</i> (2), <i>Health</i> (1), <i>Underwhelming</i> (1), <i>Pictures help</i> (1)

Agreeing Seventeen reasons were identified among those who agreed. The main was the *lack of choice*: “If signing up for a service there is a little choice. It can't be changed. The only option is to not do so”. Another reason was that the participants *wanted to use* the application: “if I wanted to use the website, I would have to consent to the privacy Policy. So I did not really considered disagreeing as an option”.

Many respondents admitted that agreement is something they always do, a *habit*, e.g., “Honestly, it's automatic. I'm not sure I even saw a disagree button. It's like a next button”. On the other hand, a few admitted that they *did not care* about privacy, e.g., “I did not provide much of personal information. My name and email are already accessible, why worry?” or stated that the policy was *not worse than others*. Some participants thought that the policy provided them with *control*, it was *somewhat clear* and *trustworthy* (e.g., “the transparency of the company made me believe they were slightly more trustworthy”).

5 Discussion

We studied the relationship between the illustration type, affect and their impact on privacy awareness and willingness to disclose (*RQ1-3*). Our results show that the policy display alters affective states. Moreover, the combined illustration type and affect interact and influence arousal. Particularly, the negative anthropomorphic representation accompanying structured text increases arousal. Yet, the same illustration type has a lower influence on arousal, when framed positively.

We did not find any effect of the illustration type on information disclosure or privacy awareness (*RQ1*). However, we identified that positive or negative framing of the designs has a significant influence on awareness (*RQ3*). It is likely that negative framing of privacy issues increases privacy awareness and influences the information recall. However, the affective framing did not alter the willingness to disclose.

Arousal was the most significant adjuster of the willingness to disclose. It seems that lower arousal reduces the desire to disclose. Stable factors, such as

privacy concerns (*RQ4*). The negative correlation between the concerns and willingness to disclose indicates that people with greater concerns manage their information more carefully. On the other hand, our results found no relationship between personality traits and privacy awareness or willingness to disclose, which is following the past research findings[9].

5.1 Practical and Theoretical Implications

Our findings confirm the results from past research that the implementation of a cartoon-like design increases attention [36, 37], but only when accompanied by affective framing. It might be that affective state mediates the relationship between the design and privacy awareness. Yet, such assumption requires future work to confirm it. Perhaps comic designs have a higher power to convey emotional meaning and improve understanding, as it has been demonstrated in Noll Webb et al. [26]. On the other hand, we have not found a direct relationship between the anthropomorphic designs and information disclosure, as suggested in Monteleone et al. [25]. We infer that the structured text display combined with affective illustrations may improve transparency and clarity of the information in privacy policies. Such findings may be implemented in the design of privacy policies to enhance legal compliance (e.g., negatively framed visual cues, which emphasize the most important aspects of data processing).

The qualitative analysis showed that the sign-up process requires improvement. Our participants expressed a need for more control and choice at an early-stage of interaction. Such findings align with past research, e.g., a lack of control as one of the privacy concerns, and call for “fine-grained” control mechanisms as shown in Sheth et al. [33]. Our participants were dissatisfied with the current designs, exhibiting desperation and indicating usability issues. Concurrently with the GDPR, this calls for granular and dynamic privacy policies. Policy designers, developers and HCI researchers should focus on identifying new ways, in which privacy policy could provide end-users with opt-in/opt-out functionality.

We examined some of the factors from the APCO framework to confirm their influence on behavioral intentions. We demonstrated that stable factors impact willingness to disclose. These findings add to the existing knowledge on the relationship between concerns and disclosure, showing that in the context of early-stage interactions, these two constructs correlate. We interpret this relationship as a demand for personalized systems recognizing and estimating level of individual privacy concerns. Such systems could trigger affect and probably decrease information disclosure (e.g., presenting less concerned users with negatively framed privacy to bring attention). However, such a personalized approach might be challenging to implement as it requires collection of personal information.

We showed that the visual presentation of privacy policies have an impact on affect, and, as a result, potential influence on privacy awareness. This finding implies that the cognitive hypotheses, such as *affect-as-feeling*, could be adapted as a backbone for the models of privacy interactions [5]. We confirmed that the

negative affect directs attention towards new information, and through activation of *cognitive feelings*, influences information recall.

5.2 Limitations and Future Work

The primary constraint of this study is the measurement of affect with self-reported measures. The research validity would increase, if it was run in the lab, enabling additional measurements, e.g., eye-tracking or electroencephalogram. Such information could improve the accuracy of affective measurements. On the other hand, running the study in the lab could decrease sample variability. As future work, we consider replicating the research in the lab environment. The sampling method might have introduced bias and gathered data only from participants interested in the research. Yet, participants gathered through a paid-for platform might be less engaged in the study, and provide answers solely to receive compensation.

Future work should expand beyond the scenario of well-being application. This could help to identify contextual dependencies of the role of visual design and affective states in the early-stage interactions.

6 Conclusion

Frequently, privacy policies leave us in a blind spot, unaware of what we agreed to. In this work, we have examined the role of visual displays in the acquisition of privacy information. We have investigated how the activation of affective states influences privacy awareness and willingness to disclose. To identify possible improvements in visual representations of privacy policies, we have examined why people decide to agree or disagree with the policies.

Our results show that affective framing and arousal alter privacy-related attitudes and behaviors. Further, our qualitative findings show that people feel hopeless during early-stage interactions, neither having control, nor choice around their data. The results can be used to design granular and dynamic consents that enable better management of personal information. Such solutions could enhance an individual's privacy, as well as help companies to comply with new regulations, e.g., the GDPR. Our findings could be used by developers and designers to enhance the usability of privacy displays and improve legal compliance. The knowledge gained in this study can be applied in future research on predictive modeling, as well as to build personalized privacy solutions.

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